

LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF UZBEKISTAN: ANALYSIS AND PROSPECTS FOR DEVELOPMENT

Kabilova Gulnora Radjabovna
Igamberdieva Dilbar Abdullaevna

Samarkand, Uzbekistan

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the analysis of the legal framework of Uzbekistan, taking into account the historical context, features of the legal system and prospects for its development. The article examines the basic principles and norms of law, as well as the role of law in ensuring stability, justice and development of society.

O'ZBEKISTONNING HUQUQIY ASOSI: TAHLILI VA TARAQQIYOT ISTIQBOLLARI

Qabilova Gulnora Radjabovna
Igamberdieva Dilbar Abdullaevna

Samarqand, O'zbekiston

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqola tarixiy sharoit, huquq tizimining xususiyatlari va rivojlanish istiqbollarini hisobga olgan holda O'zbekistonning qonunchilik bazasini tahlil qilishga bag'ishlangan. Maqolada huquqning asosiy tamoyillari va normalari, shuningdek, jamiyat barqarorligi, adolat va taraqqiyotni ta'minlashda qonunning o'rni ko'rib chiqiladi.

Introduction. The legal system of Uzbekistan has a rich history, reflecting the influence of various cultural and legal traditions. Since gaining independence in 1991, Uzbekistan has been actively working to improve its legal system in accordance with the principles of the rule of law and ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens. The legal system of Uzbekistan has ancient roots, reflecting the influence of Islamic law, traditional customs and normative acts of medieval states on the territory of modern Uzbekistan. During the Soviet period, significant changes were made to the legal system, including the introduction of new laws and institutions. After gaining independence in 1991, Uzbekistan began an active process

of developing its own legislation and reforming the legal system, taking into account national and international standards of human rights and civil liberties.

The basic principles of law in Uzbekistan are the principle of legality, State sovereignty and civil rights and freedoms. Uzbek legislation covers a wide range of legal areas, including civil, criminal, labor, family and other relations. Particular attention is paid to the protection of the rights and interests of children, women and other vulnerable groups of the population. In recent years, Uzbekistan has been carrying out active reforms in the legal sphere aimed at improving legal regulation, increasing access to justice, improving legislation and strengthening the rule of law. These reforms have a significant impact on society, contributing to the strengthening of the legal culture, the protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens, as well as the development of the economy and the social sphere. Prospects for the development of the legal system of Uzbekistan are associated with the further improvement of legislation, the strengthening of justice institutions and law enforcement agencies, as well as the promotion of national legislation in accordance with international human rights standards. An important aspect is also to ensure the accessibility of justice and the protection of the rights of citizens at all levels of society.

The legal system of Uzbekistan is based on the constitution, laws and other normative legal acts. The basis is the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which defines the basic principles of the state structure, the rights and duties of citizens, the structure of power, etc.

The legislation of Uzbekistan consists of the Constitution, laws, resolutions and orders of the President, resolutions and orders of the Cabinet of Ministers, as well as decisions and acts of the Parliament - the Oliy Majlis.

The justice system includes courts of various levels: general legal courts, administrative courts, as well as arbitration courts. The Supreme Court is the pinnacle of the judicial system.

In addition, Uzbekistan has a wide range of laws and regulations that regulate various spheres of public life, such as tax laws, labor laws, education and health legislation, etc.

Uzbekistan has joined the fundamental documents of UNESCO, such as the Hague Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict (1954), the Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage (1972), the Convention on the Means of Prohibiting and Preventing the Illicit Import, Export and Transfer of Ownership of Cultural Property (1970).

The laws on the flag (1991), coat of arms (1992) and anthem (1992) demonstrate to the whole world the norms of honor, pride, historical memory and aspirations of the peoples of Uzbekistan. The laws on the state language (1989, 1995) and citizenship (1992) are of great importance for spiritual revival. The laws on education (1997), on nature protection (1992), on copyright and related rights (1996), on the establishment of honorary titles (1996), on specially protected areas (1993), on the export and import of cultural values (1998) are being implemented. Spiritual and cultural legislation is aimed at preserving values for the people, for their spirit, asserting self-awareness of love of life, and strengthening patriotism. It is this spirit that makes any state strong.

The fifth direction is the creation of a legal framework that defines Uzbekistan as an equal subject of international relations, one of the new and practically unexplored. directions of legislative activity. Under the conditions of a totalitarian unitary system, Uzbekistan was de

facto deprived of the opportunity to directly enter the international arena, did not have its own foreign policy and foreign economic state institutions and did not have its own legislation. Uzbekistan's ratification of the main international covenants and agreements opened a new page in the history of the development of the country's foreign relations. Fundamental laws in the field of foreign policy are the laws on the procedure for appointing and recalling heads of diplomatic missions (1992) and on the establishment of diplomatic classes and ranks for diplomatic workers (1992), on international treaties (1996), on the principles of foreign policy (1997), and the Consular Charter (1996).

Conclusion. The legal system of Uzbekistan plays an important role in ensuring stability, justice and development of society. Its development and improvement in accordance with national and international standards of rights are key tasks.

The investment laws of Uzbekistan, as well as bilateral agreements on guarantees and protection of foreign investments and multilateral conventions (the Washington Conventions on the Settlement of Investment Disputes of 1965 and the Seoul Convention on Investment Insurance of 1985), contain norms of public law that determine the status of foreign private property, the legal regime of foreign investments, guarantees of foreign investments against "political" risks (nationalization, taxation, export and import duties, transfer of capital and profits, etc.), conditions for legal protection of the legitimate rights and interests of foreign investors. Specific private international investment relations are regulated by the norms of civil legislation, i.e. private law.

Thus, the modern legislation of Uzbekistan creates the legal basis for the transition period, the process of legal change of the obsolete socio-political system and economic relations, the establishment of new, democratic norms and socio-legal guarantees. Of course, the level of development and quality of the legislative system are determined not by the number of laws adopted, but by the implementation of these laws at all levels, because legal norms live and act only when they live in a person and act through him, reflect historical traditions, customs, spiritual and moral norms.

References:

1. Документы ЮНЕСКО Конвенции ЮНЕСКО / <https://icom-russia.com/data/dokumenty-yunesko/>
2. Саидов А.Х. Сравнительное правоведение (основные правовые системы современности): Учебник / Под ред. В.А. Туманова. - М.: Юристъ, 2003. -448
3. Shopulotova Z. A., Zubaydilloeva Z. K. THE VALUE OF ULTRASOUND DIAGNOSTICS IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH CHRONIC PYELONEPHRITIS //Бюллетень студентов нового Узбекистана. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 19-22.
4. Shopulotova Z. A., Zubaydilloeva Z. K. PERINATAL CARDIOLOGY: PREGNANCY AND CONGENITAL HEART DEFECTS //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 9. – С. 55-59.
5. Shopulotova Z., Shopulotov S., Kobilova Z. MODERN ASPECTS OF HYPERPLASTIC PRO //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 787-791.

6. Shopulotova Z. A., Zubaydilloeva Z. K., Khudoyarova D. R. COMORBID EVENTS IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH PYELONEPHRITIS AND PREVENTION OF THESE CONDITIONS //Бюллетень педагогов нового Узбекистана. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 35-38.
7. Khamzaevna Z. Z. ROLE OF BETA-BLOCKERS IN THE TREATMENT OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION Zubaydilloeva Zarina Khamzaevna //Independent Publishing Network Ltd Mailing address–MB# 1869, PO BOX 229, EGHAM, TW20 8WZ, UK. – 2020. – С. 20.
8. Khudoyarova D. R., Shopulotova Z. A., Solieva Z. M. PREVENTION OF COMPLICATIONS IN PREGNANT WOMEN WITH CHRONIC PYELONEPHRITIS //Бюллетень студентов нового Узбекистана. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 25-29.
9. KHUDOYAROVA D. R. et al. ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF WOMEN'S LIFE OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE WITH SURGICAL MENOPAUSE //БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ. – 2020. – С. 48.
10. Shopulotova Z. A., Khudoyarova D. R., Solieva Z. M. PREGNANT WOMEN WITH PYELONEPHRITIS //American Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development. – 2023. – Т. 15. – С. 268-271.
11. Серебренников М.А. Становление новой системы законодательства Узбекистана// Актуальные проблемы науки в исследованиях студентов, ученых, практиков Сборник научных статей студентов, студент магистратуры, практиков, подготовленный по итогам Международной научно-практической конференции. Ижевск, 2021.- С.766-772
12. Становление новой системы законодательства Узбекистана// <https://jurisprudence.club/teoriya-gosudarstva-prava-uchebnik/stanovlenie-novoy-sistemyi-zakonodatelstva.html>
13. Ibragimov S. et al. HORMONAL IMBALANCE IN FEMALES UNDER CHRONIC PSYCHOLOGICAL STRESS: A MULTIDIMENSIONAL EXPLORATION //Collection of scientific papers «SCIENTIA». – 2023. – №. November 17, 2023; Sydney, Australia. – С. 217-219.
14. Shopulotova Z., Kobilova Z., Bazarova F. TREATMENT OF COMPLICATED GESTATIONAL PYELONEPHRITIS IN PREGNANTS //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 630-634.
15. Shopulotova Z., Kobilova Z., Shopulotov S. URINATION DISORDERS IN PREGNANT WOMEN //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 774-777.
16. Shopulotova Z., Kobilova Z., Shopulotov S. NEW OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE TREATMENT OF HYPERACTIVE BLADDER SYNDROME //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 770-773.
17. Shopulotova Z., Kobilova Z., Shopulotov S. INFLUENCE OF PREECLAMPSIA ON SOMATIC DISEASES //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 778-780.
18. Shopulotova Z., Shopulotov S., Kobilova Z. MODERN ASPECTS OF HYPERPLASTIC PRO //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 787-791.
19. Shopulotova Z., Shopulotov S., Kobilova Z. MODERN VIEWS ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF OZONE THERAPY //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D12. – С. 781-786.
20. Radzhabovna K. G., Abdullaevna I. D., Khamzaevna K. Z. NEW UZBEKISTAN: COOPERATION OF UZBEKISTAN WITH ASIAN COUNTRIES //European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 12. – С. 98-102.